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SCHEMA OF DEMAND THEORY (BERNOULI TO MARSHALL 1738 TO 1890)

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ABSTRACT

The significance and validity of both problems and methods cannot be fully grasped without having knowledge of the previous problems and methods to which they are the (tentative) response. Therefore, it is necessary to have the knowledge of history of any science before taking any current work. This paper investigates how the value and price of any commodity is determined besides, the phases of the development of demand theory. Development of the theory of demand has taken a long way to come into being. This paper finds that Classical theorists did not give consumption a place equal to that held by production and distribution in the schema of science. Jevons changed the emphasis to demand and depended upon utility to explain value. Marginal utility theorists introduced the psychological element and developed the theory of utility as a diminishing, and of sacrifice as an increasing function of the quantity of the commodity. The subjective theory of value was an attempt to use psychological introspection to go behind the observed behaviour of demand, supply and price. It sought to explain every relationship between demand, supply and price in terms of a more fundamental relationship between pleasure, pain and the means of satisfying wants. The theory of demand developed by Marshall was richer since he did not merely link marginal utility theory with the theory of demand in a very convincing manner but also explained the factors, which lie behind observed choice.

Key words: Schema, Demand, Supply, Marshall, Bernouli

INTRODUCTION:

The significance and validity of both problems and methods cannot be fully grasped without knowledge of the previous problems and methods to which they are the (tentative) response. Therefore, it is necessary to have the knowledge of history of any science before taking any current work. The highest claim that can be made for the history of any science or of science in general is that it teaches us much about the ways of the human mind. Development of the theory of demand has taken a long way to come into being. We know that, from Aristotelian roots¹, this theory was developed by the Scholastics, who were entitled to the credit for having developed the theory of price (Schumpeter 1961: 60), whose analysis of value and price in terms of 'utility and scarcity' lacked nothing but the marginal apparatus (ibid 1054). Classical economists emphasised production, supply and cost while modern theory concerns itself mainly with consumption, demand and utility. The marginal utility concept was introduced to affect this shift of emphasis. William Stanley Jevons made the laws of human wants the basis of political economy as he held that "the theory of economics must begin with a correct theory of consumption." The Classical theorists did not give consumption a place equal to that held by production and

distribution in the schema of science. They placed special emphasis on the supply side. Jevons changed the emphasis to demand and depended upon utility to explain value². They often referred to the paradox of the value, which they were unable to solve. Classical economists, held utility as a necessary condition for the existence of exchange value. But they resorted to different factors for the explanation of exchange value. Their real value theory, which was meant to explain exchange value, was a cost theory. The whole classical system was based on four main pillars:

1. Malthusian Population Theory;
2. The Wages Fund Theory;
3. The Theory of Rent; and
4. The Labour (and subsequently cost of production) Theory of Value.

Mill held the view that cost of production is the ultimate regulator of value, not demand and supply. Cost of production was further resolvable into labour cost (since capital was also treated as accumulated past labour) Mill concluded. In the words of Arrow and Starrett, “The course of real wages was certainly in consistent with any subsistence theory by the middle of the nineteenth century.” The value placed by the market on labour could not be explained by its cost of production; the most natural alternative was to explain wages³ by the productivity of labour, an explanation only useful if labour was only intrinsically scarce.....what led to the downfall of the classical theory was “the failure to explain either absolute or real wages”. Moreover, they also failed to clarify the relationship between wages and productivity and ultimately consumer demand was suppressed in it.

Marginal utility theorists viz. Jevons, Menger and Walras adopted Bentham’s felicific calculus, introduced the psychological element and developed the theory of utility as a diminishing, and of sacrifice as an increasing function of the quantity of the commodity. The prime representatives of the neo-classicists, Alfred Marshall endeavoured to settle the controversy between two principle schools of thought on this crucial question (whether value is governed by utility or cost of production) by his famous analogy of the two blades of a pair of scissors. He resolved it by saying, “that, as a general rule, the shorter the period which we are considering the greater must be the share of attention which is given to the influence of demand on value, and longer the period, the more important will be the influence of cost of production on value.”

The subjective theory of value was an attempt to use psychological introspection to go behind the observed behaviour of demand, supply and price. It sought to explain every relationship between demand, supply and price in terms of a more fundamental relationship between pleasure, pain and the means of satisfying wants. Utility theorists’ idea of margin played a crucial role as an instrument of maximisation analysis. Optimisation became the essence of the problem with the marginal utility theorists. It contributes towards turning economics into a rigorous mathematical discipline⁴. The marginal economics shifted its emphasis from total quantity to small changes in these total. It was the ‘subjective’ or utility theory of price that had the wind until the influence of the “An Enquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of the Nations (1776)” by Adam Smith (who is called the father of economics) and especially of David Ricardo’s Principles – asserted itself. The essential elements of modern analysis – the emphasis on demand and utility and formulation of the law of diminishing

utility – were developed by a number of eighteenth and nineteenth century authors. The concept of marginal utility had been independently discovered over and over again in different countries in between 1738 and 1874.

The concept of marginal utility goes back to the writing of Bernoulli, Bentham, Senior, and Lloyd. However, it was only Lloyd who made any substantial use of it. It was again discovered by Dupit, Gossen, and Jennings who used it to throw light on consumer behaviour. But it was only in 1870s that the systematisation and refinement of the subjective approach took place. “The term ‘marginal revolution’ is usually taken to refer to the nearly simultaneous but completely independent discovery in the early 1870s by Jevons, Menger, and Walras of the principles of the diminishing marginal utility as the fundamental building block of a new kind of static micro economics.” It was only in the writings of Jevons, Menger, and Walras that the subjective satisfactions were made the starting point of explanations of the relative price. The conspicuous novelty in their works was the replacement of the labour theory of value by the marginal utility theory of value. Jevons stood for a much more decisive role for consumer demand and utility in value theory and for productivity in wage and distribution theory. His marginal utility theory of value help to resolve certain long standing paradoxes involved in the classical definitions of value. The exposition of the celebrated trinity definitely marked a turning point in the transition from the classical economics to the marginal economics. Their analysis resolved itself into a study of variations in utility. They found that the crucial important point in the variations of utility lay at the margin. Marginal utility was the unifying principle of all economic reasoning in their works. It was the effort of these men that initiated the ‘marginal revolution’ in 1870s. The ‘marginal revolution’ is sometimes called ‘Jevonian Revolution’ because Jevon’s work represented a clean break with classical tradition. W. Jaffe prefers to call ‘marginal revolution’ a ‘marginal revolt’ or ‘marginal insurrection’ since in his view “the revolution in standard economics was not an accomplished fact for several decades after the 1870s.” According to him, what happened in the 1870s could be viewed as marginal utility innovation. Marginal revolution of the 1870s thus stood for a breakthrough in theory and technique of economic science.

Development of the theory of demand for the period from 1738-1890 include early utility theorists: Daniel Bernoulli (1738), Jeremy Bentham (1789), William Foster Lloyd (1833), Nassau William Senior (1836), Arsene Jules Etienne Juvenal Dupit (1844), and Harmann Heinrich Gossen (1854). The first four early utility theorists may be designated as the forerunners, the last two as the anticipators of the doctrine. These writers adhered to no school of thought, and with sole exception of Bentham, did not appreciably influence the fuller development of the theory. Daniel Bernoulli, the eminent scientists, suggested the hypothesis that the economic significance to individual of an additional dollar is inversely proportional to the number of dollars he already has. In 1738, Bernoulli discovered marginal utility for the first time. Marginal utility is an important conception known to modern economists as the diminishing marginal utility of money – a conception on which many important arguments are founded relating to taxation and ideal distribution of wealth. Bernoulli was one of the first economists who used mathematical methods in economics. The other economists, according to Schumpeter, who antedated Von Thunen and Cournot in this regards were Becarria and Isnard. Schumpeter further pointed out that Thunen was the first to use the calculus as a form of economic reasoning. Bentham inter alia, formulated psychology of “economic man” and of the calculus of pleasure and pain. Jeremy Bentham influenced economic theory by setting forth systematically the principle of utility, or the ‘greatest happiness.’

William Foster Lloyd undertook the analysis of utility, devised the tool of margin and virtually illustrated its use for the problem of pricing. He repeatedly argues that, in the final analysis, the term 'utility' signifies a feeling of the mind, which shows itself always at the margin of separation between the satisfied and unsatisfied wants. Lloyd is the originator of the marginal utility principle of value, though his position as such has been challenged. Claims have been made for, among others, Senior who is described as "the most distinguished of a group of economists" who stuck to the utility explanation of the value in opposition to the position of the English Classicists in the first half of the nineteenth century. Like Bernoulli, Nassau William Senior uses the word 'wealth' to connote economic goods. Wealth comprises all those things, which are:

- i. Transferable;
- ii. Limited in supply;
- iii. Capable of producing pleasure or preventing pain, directly or indirectly.

Senior talks about sources of desires. He assumes "the love of variety" and "the love of distinction" as two chief influences on human nature. He classified the desires into two broad categories viz. the desire for variety and the desire for distinction. The desire for variety manifests necessities of life – provided to support a level of bare animal existence. The desire for variety quickly reaches its highest point while the desire for distinction presents itself in tastes for "comforts and conveniences" which are "absolutely insatiable where they exist, and seem to increase with every improvement in civilisation." Senior emphasises diversity as against quantity as the main aim of human desires. Senior meant by the demand of the commodity "the degree in which its possession is desired." He took the case of a deficient wheat harvest, which increased the demand for oats and barley. "The deficiency of wheat would not give to the consumers of oats and barley any increased power of purchasing nor would the quantity purchased or consumed be increased." But the demand for them could be said to increase in the sense that they are desired now in greater degree than before (or in other words, the utility of a given quantity of them had increased).

Jules Dupit was an engineer and mathematician. Thinking on the most advantageous maintenance of public works he got at two different notions about utility: "absolute utility" which is the amount a buyer is willing to pay for certain increment of a commodity and "relative or definitive utility" which is the difference between the absolute utility (demand price) and the purchase price. He clearly saw in the latter the economic basis of many public policies. On the basis of his utility analysis Dupit also advanced economic justification for discriminatory price policy – to borrow his own phrase, "all the frauds that go in business" – as a means of maximising revenue. In the utility tradition, Dupit is the first and the only economist before Marshall and Pigou to attempt to build a "systematic welfare theory." He annotates Smith's distinction between value-in-use and value-in-exchange. The latter is the exchangeable worth of a commodity, the former is its utility or its capacity to satisfy human wants, which can exceed or fall short of the exchangeable worth. This variant of utility is termed as "absolute utility," is the real utility and is independent of the market price. Relative utility is the difference between the consumer's absolute utility (expressed in money) and the purchase price he has to pay in exchange. Dupit postulates the law of diminishing utility and develops the utility function, which is monotonically increasing negatively accelerated function of the quantity of the goods. The next step was to

show that the quantities of goods demanded are decreasing function of price. This is illustrated in diagram 1. In the diagram 1 NQ is the curve of consumption. OY axis scaled various quantities of commodities consumed, corresponding to various prices indicated horizontally on OX axis. ON represents the quantity when price is zero and OQ the price at which consumption falls to zero. Demand schedule is represented by $n p$, $n' p'$, $n'' p''$ and $n''' p'''$ corresponding to prices $O p$, $O p'$, $O p''$, and $O p'''$ respectively. The slope of the curve is convex to the origin. Dupit argument is based on two generalisations, supported by two empirical observation of human behaviour in the market:

- i. consumption expands with every fall in price and vice-versa;
- ii. increase in consumption due to fall in the price will be greater, the lower the initial price.

Diagram 1: Relationship between quantity consumed and price

Source: Kaur, Upinder Jit, “Development of Theory of Demand,” Bernoulli to Marshall.

Original source: Jules Dupit, “On the Measurement of Public Works,” International Economic Papers (1952), Vol.II.

Dupit did not mention Augustin Cournot anywhere in his work though his demand curve is similar to that of Cournot drawn by him six years before (1838). Later on Marshall draw the similar diagram except that he had measured quantity on X axis and price on Y axis. He also qualified it with the assumption of constancy of marginal utility of money. Dupit developed the curve of consumption (demand curve) and invented the apparatus of consumer’s surplus (his ‘relative utility’). Hermann Heinrich Gossen, a German mathematical economist of note is memorable for mathematical formulation of the ‘Principle of Diminishing Utility’ and of the ‘conditions of maximum satisfaction’. These two formulations are known as the first and second laws of Gossen. Gossen’s second law is derived from the first law (which is a postulate) with the additional assumption that all wants cannot be fully satisfied and the point of satiety is reached only when the consumption has gone through all phases of diminishing intensity. Laws are set down after a brief comment on the attribute of utility.

He regards utility purely as a relation between “useful objects” and person. Useful objects of the external world are broadly classified into three classes:

- i. finished goods ready for consumption i.e.; an apple, shirt etc.;
- ii. semi-finished goods such as wheat, cloth, and goods which are only subsidiary sources of pleasure e.g. a tobacco-pipe which has no utility apart from tobacco (complementary goods in modern technology);
- iii. all those materials which are indirectly productive of pleasure i.e.; capital goods, raw materials, and means of communication like railways.

The premises from which Gossen’s theory derives are solemnly utilitarian. He builds upwards on the epicurean base that “man desires to enjoy his life in the raising of his life’s enjoyment to the maximum.”

An attempt has been made to give a geometrical expression to the entire theory of economic equilibrium on the two dimensional basis. In all Gossen has employed 24 figures. Here only four figures in diagram 2 are illustrated to explain his basic ideas. The figures in diagram 2 illustrate different shapes:

- i. Straight;
- ii. Convex to the origin;
- iii. Concave to the origin; and
- iv. Undulating.

All figures from i – iv in diagram 2 illustrate law of diminishing pleasure. In each figure the co-ordinate axes represent the time a pleasure lasts and the corresponding magnitude⁵ of pleasure. The time is shown horizontally along a b and the magnitude of pleasure vertically along a c. By connecting the extremities of the ordinates, which if drawn, will successively go on shortening down to zero, we have the time c b, which represents the continued decrease in the magnitude of the pleasure enjoyed. Gossen was the first writer to formulate explicitly the ‘fundamental principle of marginal utility theory.’ Gossen gave the economic world what Walras called the mathematical equilibrium: his theory of pleasure and pain establish the condition of absolute maximum, which were later elaborated by Jevons into the theory of relative maximum and by Walras into the theory of general equilibrium. Jevons, Menger and Walras restated Gossen’s, Bentham’s and Bernoulli’s law of satiable wants, in doing so they all treated utility (or the satisfaction of wants) as a psychological fact that is known to us from introspection, and as the ‘cause of value,’ they felt little or no compunction about its measurability, and they all made the utility of every commodity to its possessor depend upon the quantity of the commodity alone (ibid 1055).

But none of the early utility theorists had devoted themselves to the development of the demand theory. Bernoulli, who discovered marginal utility for the first time in 1738, was not an economist. Bentham’s interest was restricted to the calculus of pleasure and pain for policy implications only. Adam Smith and, following him, practically all the English ‘Classics’ with the exception of Senior evidently did not realise the possibilities of

utility approach to the phenomenon of economic value and were content to turn from ‘value-in-use’ with reference to the paradox of value that should not have been a paradox any more (ibid 1054). Senior had a clear idea of total utility and diminishing marginal utility. But he did not perceive the importance of the law of diminishing marginal utility.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Diagram 2: Geometrical expression to the entire theory of economic equilibrium

Source: Kaur, Upinder Jit, “Development of Theory of Demand,” Bernoulli to Marshall.

Original Source: Entwicklung

After Cournot, Dupit was the first to use the demand curve in economics. Dupit identified the marginal utility curve as the demand curve without using the necessary logical steps to derive the latter from the former. Gossen was the first writer to formulate explicitly the fundamental principle of marginal utility theory, now known as

equi-marginal principle. But Gossen proceeded to formulate the conditions of individual equilibrium without taking recourse to the law of demand. On the other hand, the demand theorist presented a sophisticated theory of demand but they did not take recourse to the theory of utility to provide the rationale for the downward slope of the demand curve. They based their demand function on observation. It was thus left to later utility theorists – the founder of the marginal utility theory of demand to derive the negatively sloping demand curve from the law of diminishing marginal utility. The great founders of the neo-classical school, Carl Menger, W.S. Jevons, and Leon Walras, and their precursors A. A. Cournot and H. H. Gossen understood the glaring omission of demand from the classical model. They took as an expository point of departure a model, which was the polar opposite of the classical model of pure exchange. It was Jevons, Menger and Walras who turned the scattered fragments of earlier utility analysis into a comprehensive theory of value, exchange and distribution. Jevons “Theory of Exchange” is based directly on his “Theory of Utility⁶.” Although Jevons marginal utility analysis leads directly to the notion of a derived demand curve yet he never tried to derive a demand curve. He wanted to apply the equation of exchange to the case of a competitive market, but could not tackle it, as he did not derive demand curve from utility curve. He also failed to explain how the collective marginal utility was determined. It was thus left to Walras and Marshall to show the connection between marginal utility, demand and price under competitive conditions. Menger brought the corpus of economic theory within the bonds of utility analysis more successfully than Jevons and Walras. Menger’s analysis of demand is the best formulated up to that time. It is even loaded with germs of Edgeworth’s contract curve and Cournot-Marshall’s price elasticity of demand. Menger endeavoured to build a theory of price⁷ on his analysis of utility. Price is fixed by marginal demands and offers. Whenever there is occasion for exchange, each individual formulates some quantitatively determinate ratio in which he is willing to exchange. This ratio reflects the ratio of his subjective value. This is how Menger relates the supply and demand theory of the market price to the “ultimate” theory of subjective value⁸. Both Menger and Jevons put their analysis of utility first and then worked forward to arrive at a theory of price. However, Walras started with price and worked backward to find demand then analysed relations between price and demand on the one hand and utility on the other. Technically, his theory of prices is developed directly from demand (supply) schedules. He used utility as a way of understanding demand schedules and as an indication that equilibrium price is also the equation of maximum satisfaction. Unlike Cournot’s demand curve, $D = f(p)$, which was empirically derived. Walras deduced the demand curve from the condition of maximum satisfaction. Geometrically, if price and quantity are on X and Y axis respectively, and we draw a demand curve as a decreasing function of price; the extensive utility is the intercept of the demand curve on the Y (quantity) axis. The normal convention, which puts the independent variables (the variable that does the explaining) on the horizontal axis and the dependent variable (the variable that is explained) on the vertical axis, calls for price to be plotted on the horizontal axis and quantity on the vertical axis.

The axis reversal – now enshrined by a century of usage – arose as follows. The analysis of the competitive market that we use today stems from the French economist Leon Walras (1834-1910), in whose theory quantity was the dependent variable. Graphical analysis in economics, however, was popularised by the English economist Alfred Marshall (1842-1924), in whose theory price was the dependent variable (Lipsey 1999: 37). The Walras’s demand curve is shown in diagram 3. The slope of the demand curve (“the limit of the ratio of a

decrease in demand to an increase in price”) depends on intensive utility⁹. The slope of the demand curve is simply a ratio of two quantities, viz; the increase in price and the resulting diminution in demand.

Diagram 3: Walras' demand curve

Rather than deriving the demand curve from analysis of utility and the supply curve from the analysis of cost and then introducing the process of mutual causation of demand, supply and price, Walras starts with a negatively sloping demand curve, derives the supply curve of one commodity from the demand curve of other commodity which is offered in exchange and then shows that the competitive price will be determined at the point of intersection of the two curves where demand curve and supply curves are equal. Walras shows that there is a direct relationship between demand and price but none between supply and price. Walras uses the term effective demand¹⁰ to indicate “demand for a definite amount of a commodity at a definite price.” Walras was the first economist who succeeded in linking utility and demand. He was able to derive negatively sloping demand curve from the law of diminishing marginal utility but he stood the logic on its head by deriving the conditions of market equilibrium from given demand curves and then deriving the latter from utility curves. He used utility as a way of understanding demand schedules, and as an indication that equilibrium price is also the equation of maximum satisfaction.

Among the founders, Marshall alone seems to have proceeded in the right direction. He was one of the originators of the marginal utility theory of demand. He was the first economist to link marginal utility theory with the theory of demand in a convincing manner. However, Marshall early discussion of demand was completely independent of utility analysis. In fact Marshall criticises Adam Smith in his paper “An Early Essay on the Theory of Value” for regarding the ‘value-in-use’ of a thing as ‘depending upon its utility.’ In the same vein he criticises Ricardo and Mill for confounding the use of a term “supply of and demand for a commodity” in relation to price determination. On the other hand, in his review article of Jevons’ Theory, Marshall criticises Jevons for holding the view that value depends solely upon utility. Again in his article “On Mr. Mill’s theory of Value,” Marshall did not use the term utility at all. Marshall wrote this article in defence of Mill’s theory of

value in which Mill had not taken recourse to any theory of utility. The evolution of Marshall's thought with regard to the theory of demand can be seen clearly in his writings "An Early Essay on the Theory of Value" written about 1869, his review article in 1872, his two papers on "The Pure Theory of Foreign Trade," and "The Pure Theory of Domestic Values." His first book "The Economics of Industry (1879)," and his famous book "Principles of Economics (1890)," went through eight editions during his life time, the last one appearing in 1920¹¹ bring out clearly how his ideas developed on the subject. The paper on "Foreign Trade" also contains Marshall's device of offer curves,¹² which portray Mill's law of reciprocal demand graphically. "The paper on "Domestic Values" is concerned with the cause, which determines the relative values of commodities produced in the same country under the action of free competition." It quotes from the author's earlier article in the fortnightly review (April 1876) to draw attention to "the great central law of economic science¹³." It becomes obvious from "Domestic Values" that Marshall began his discussion of value with the introduction of demand and supply curves. It was only afterwards that he came around to the use of the idea of the utility. He then interpreted the demand curve of an individual as the individual's utility curve for the good. The paper on "Domestic Values" also reveals that Marshall first employed the idea of marginal utility in connection with consumer's rent¹⁴.

The idea of marginal utility played an inconsequential role in his work until the publication of the "Principles of Economics." In the works published before 1890, Marshall was concerned only with drawing "the demand curve of the commodity for the whole market." No attempt was made to develop such a curve from the individual demand curves and base the latter on the subjective analysis of consumer behaviour, which made its appearance in the "Principles of Economics." It was only in the "Principles of Economics" that marginal utility came forth as an important and integral part of his economic analysis. The theory of demand is developed painstakingly into a scientific formulation that seeks to describe as also explain how consumers during a given time and given conditions. Marshall's method is logical, he makes assumption and then using the technique of marginal analysis derives the individual demand curve and the market demand curve. Marshall built his theory of demand on the following assumptions:

- i. Utility is cardinal;
- ii. Constant marginal utility of money;
- iii. Utility of every commodity is a function of that commodity alone;
- iv. Utility functions were additive.

In the beginning, utility, both total and marginal was considered a psychic reality, a feeling that was evident from introspection, independent of any external observation and a directly measurable quantity. It was believed to be the opinion of Menger and Bohm Bawerk. Marshall measures utility indirectly by their observable effects, a pleasure for instance by the sum of money a man is prepared to give up obtaining it rather than going without it. Later on both theories of utility measurement merged into one conception, which is called theory of cardinal utility (Schumpeter 1961: 1060) .

Utility of every commodity is a function of that commodity alone. Edgeworth did away with this assumption, and made the utility enjoyed by an individual a function of all the commodities that enter his budget (ibid 1061). Marshall welcomed this step coldly, perhaps he thought of the mathematical complications involved in making the equations of utility theory partial instead of ordinary differential equations. Marshall attempted to make the measurement of utility operational by means of the consumer's rent (ibid 1060). Although, Marshall recognised the existence of rival products and complementary products, he retained this assumption and ignored the interdependence of utilities.

The retention of the assumption of an additive utility function by Marshall was important in the sense that it enabled him to present the negatively demand curve as a necessary corollary to the law of diminishing marginal utility. The derivation of the demand curve from underlying utility curve was based on the notion of additive utility functions.

From the law of diminishing marginal utility Marshall deduces the demand schedule, which is later translated into a curve for which he suggests the name demand curve and restates the theorem as follows:

The larger the amount of a thing a person has the less, other things being equal (i.e.; the purchasing power of money, and the amount of money at his command being equal), will be the price he will pay for a little more of it, or in other words his marginal demand price for it diminishes. His demand becomes efficient, only when the price, which he is willing to offer, reaches that at which others are willing to sell.

We may now join strands of thought and sum up the discussion on the development of the theory of demand. There are two alternative approaches to deduce the demand function:

- i. The empirical approach or observation approach;
- ii. The subjective approach.

The empirical approach consists of correlating quantity demanded and price from statistically recorded data pertaining to successive observations taken over a period of time. The subjective approach is the method of marginal utility theorists in which the demand function delineates the same relationship, but at a single moment of time, and this approach is based on the fundamental psychological postulates.

There are two principal authors, viz; Cournot and Mill, in the period covered who choose the first method and refused to recede to any theory of utility. Cournot and Mill both presented a well developed theory of demand but they based their demand curves on observation. Cournot started from the observable fact that there are systematic relationship between prices, production and consumption of commodities. He was the first economist to assume that the function $F(p)$, which expresses the law of demand.....is a continuous function. He presented the idea of demand as a function of price $F(p)$ and was the first to portray it graphically. In the diagram 4, p and d represent abscissa and the ordinates respectively¹⁵. The relationship between p and d is delineated by the curve $a n b$ is the market demand curve and not the individual demand curve which can be, and is usually, discontinuous. We will assume that the function $F(p)$is a continuous function i.e.; a function which does not

pass suddenly from one value to another, but which takes in passing all intermediate values. The triangle $on t$, formed by the tangent nt and the radius vector on , is isosceles, so that..... $oq = qt$. This has been introduced by Cournot to indicate that the value of the function $p F(p)$ will be maximum at point n . In a later-day language, the price elasticity of demand at point n is unity, indicating that the total revenue will be maximum when the price is oq and the quantity demanded qn . Cournot makes it sufficiently clear that the law of demand can at best be only directional and changes in the demand for an article cannot be related to changes in its price in any precise manner. Here is an excerpt from his chapter on demand.

The price of violins or of astronomical telescopes might fall one-half and yet probably the demand would not double,.....on the contrary, firewood, which is one of the most useful articles, could probably double in price, from the progress of clearing land or increase in population, long before the annual consumption of fuel would be halved; as a large number of consumers disposed to cut down other expenses rather than get along without firewood.

Diagram 4: Cournot's Demand Curve

Cournot presented the original idea of demand as a function of price.....a contribution which was proved to be of permanent value and influence. He was the first to develop demand function and price function. He was also the first to construct theory of price and markets. Cournot's supply curve "expressing the quantity that would be offered at any assigned price" is made up of the functions expressing the cost of production to each producer, in such a way as to bring out clearly the principle that the price is equal to the cost of production to the last unit produced. Thus without using the terms "marginal revenue" and "marginal cost" Cournot was clearly in possession of both these concepts. Like Cournot, Mill also refused to provide the law of demand with a subjective explanation. Mill's contribution to the theory of demand is a part of his value¹⁶. He made two important contributions to the analysis of demand. First, he presented the law of demand in a manner, which

would bring out its role in the process of exchange clearly. Secondly, he classified the concept of price elasticity of demand without defining or naming it. Mill means by the term demand, the quantity of the commodity “for which at the market price, purchaser can be found.” He emphasised “demand to be capable of comparison with supply, must be taken to mean, not a wish, nor a power, but a quantity. Neither is it at any time a fixed quantity, but varies with the price.” A beggar may desire a diamond, but his desire, however great will have no influence on the price. Demand (in the technical sense) is therefore, the wish to possess, combined with the power of purchasing. Defining supply as, “the quantity offered for sale.” Mill shows how the interaction of demand and supply in a competitive regime leads to the establishment of market value, which equalises the demand and the supply. Mill’s theory approaches the modern theory so closely that it evoked from Maurice Dobb the observation that in major respects that his own work was much nearer to Marshall than it was to Ricardo. Although Mill had in mind the distinction between demand determined and supply determined prices¹⁷, but he did not elaborate it. He did not introduce time element into his analysis. It was thus left to show that all problems of value can be treated in terms of demand and supply. After assessing the role of demand and supply in the formation of domestic values, Mill assesses their relative role in the formation of international values. Here he involves two concepts, viz. reciprocal demand and the concept of price elasticity of demand. Mill was the first to combine a theory reciprocal demand with Ricardian comparative costs in order to show how the gains of trade were shared between the countries concerned. While examining the “effect of improvements in production on international value,” he introduced the notion of price elasticity of demand, the first clear statement of it in the history of economic ideas. Mill was aware of the total revenue criterion of demand elasticity. The influence of cheapness on demand is divided into three categories: elastic, unit elastic and inelastic. Following the ideas of Cournot and Mill, Marshall employed the demand function as an empirical function (which implies its being deduced from recorded data) in his earlier writing. Marshall, later influenced by Jevons widened his formulation to provide the rationale for the negative slope of the demand curve in terms of marginal utility analysis. Cournot and Mill rejected utility analysis of demand function. Their main objection was that utility is a subjective thing, hence incapable of precise enumeration and measurement. It is true that almost all of the main elements of the Marshall’s theory are to be found in economic literature before his work appeared. However, Marshall was virtually the first author to derive the demand curve clearly and explicitly from the utility functions. He also developed the concept of elasticity of demand, the embryos of which are found in Cournot’s and Mill’s analyses. The theory of demand developed by Marshall was richer since he did not merely linked marginal utility theory with the theory of demand in a very convincing manner but also explained the factors, which lies behind observed choice. Marshallian cross of demand and supply curves was the analytical device that integrated his whole work. Thus it can be seen that Marshall advanced towards the marginal utility theory after deploying the demand function as an empirical function. Only in his book “Principles of Economics” published in 1890 did marginal utility emerged as an important and integral part of his economic analysis. The utility analysis provides the rationale for the downward slope of the demand curve. The marginal utility theory was indebted to provide a psychological explanation of the cause of demand, supply and price. Marshall made it very clear that the character of the forces that play upon demand on the one side and upon supply on the other side vary with the length of the time under consideration. Marshall thus enunciated that a theorist should follow the scheme of demand and supply in all exchanges. He used utility analysis to give an

account of demand and the cost of production to give an account of supply. In this way Marshall was able to find room for the utility analysis and the cost analysis within a single body of theory.

Notes:

1. Aristotle based his economic analysis squarely upon wants and their satisfactions. Starting from the economy of self-sufficient households, he then introduced division of labour, barter, and money- to overcome the difficulties of barter (Schumpeter 1961: 60).

2. Jevons opposed the Ricardian views that labour cost was the determinant of value. He also criticised the assumption of homogeneity of labour. Jevons held that labour was a variable, the value of which “must be determined by the value of the produce, not the value of the produce by that of labour.” On the theory of value Walras writes: The science of economics offers three major solutions to the problem of the origin of value. The first, that of Adam Smith, Ricardo and McCulloch is the English solution, which traces the origin of value to labour. This solution is too narrow, because it fails to attribute value to things, which in fact do have value. The second solution that of Condillac and J. B. Say is the French solution that traces the origin of value to utility.

This solution is too broad, because it attributes value to things, which, in fact, have no value. Finally, third solution, that of Burlamqui and Walras’s father A. A. Walras traces the origin of value to scarcity (rarete). This is the correct solution.

3. Both Ricardo and Mill based their theory of wages on hard-line Malthusian law of population. In face of this subsistence level or natural wages theories became altogether nebulous. Thus, one support of classical distribution structure was removed and as a result classical distribution theory was adrift.

4. Dr. Black states “ The theory of Political Economy marks a watershed in the development of economic thought mainly because of two outstanding characteristics in it- its introduction into economics of psychological hedonism on the one hand, and mathematical and quantitative techniques on the other. The first of these, it seems to me, can be directly traced to the utilitarian philosophy of Jeremy Bentham and second to the mathematical logic of Augustus De Morgan.”

5. A quantity or magnitude is defined as anything that is capable of being greater or smaller than some other things. This property implies only transitivity, asymmetry and aliorelativity (the last term meaning that no things can be greater or smaller than itself.) It also covers the relation of equality, which is however, a symmetrical and reflexive (the latter term meaning the opposite of aliorelative). See Joseph A. Schumpeter (1961), “History of Economic Analysis,”p.1062.

6. Jevons’ theory is built up largely upon the utilitarian ideas of Bentham. Though, among the important influences acknowledged, Jevons mentions, besides, Bentham, also Senior and Jennings. He was fully appreciative of the shifting and complex nature of the economic data. Though he approached economic theory primarily as a deductive economist, he also reasoned on the basis of his inductive studies. He was utilitarian and

he remained utilitarian to the end of his life. He modelled his theory of utility upon his “Theory of Pleasure and Pain.” He invented the word “disutility” to signify the opposite of utility. Disutility corresponds to the production of pain, which can arise from any disagreeable things like ashes or sewage. Such things Jevons named “discommodities.” The three notions through which utility passes are thus designated by sign +, 0, and – (utility, inutility or disutility).

7. Menger’s theory is entirely non-hedonistic. It only assumes the economic use of scarce means for the most effective satisfaction of human needs. He emphasised utility rather than supply and demand in his price. Menger was primarily a deductive economist and upheld abstraction in theoretical analysis. But he also recognised the usefulness of historical research and induction. Menger’s pioneer work on marginal utility was in the field of pure theory.

8. Like Jevons, Menger rejected the labour theory of value of the classics. He showed that the value of a good arises from its use in consumption, not because it cost so much to produce. Menger was the first utility theorist to distinguish clearly between utility and value in use. Subsequently Menger explained use value and exchange value. By “use value” Menger means the importance of the goods acquire for use because they directly assures of the satisfaction of needs that would not be provided if we did not have goods at our commands. By “exchange value” Menger signifies “the importance that goods acquire for us because their possession assures the same result indirectly” by way of exchange for other goods.

9. Walras uses “intensity of wants” and “intensive utility” as alternative expression. Geometrically the intensive utility can be marked off as the intercept of the demand curve on x (price) axis, if we lay off, as before, price on x and quantity on y axis. “The intensity of the last want satisfied by any given quantity consumed of a commodity.” Walras defined “rarete” as the “intensity of the last want satisfied by the quantity possessed of a commodity.” In order to express the “rarete” Walras attributes “to each trading party an equation or curve relative to each consumer’s goods or service” and express the “rarete” as a decreasing function of the quantity of the commodity consumed.

10. Walras states “The effective demand for or offer of one commodity in exchange for another is equal respectively to the effective offer of or demand for the second commodity multiplied by its price in terms of the first.”

11. The dates of various editions of Marshall’s “Principles of Economics” are 1st ed. 1890; 2nd ed. 1891; 3rd ed. 1895; 4th ed. 1898; 5th ed. 1907; 6th ed. 1910; 7th ed. 1916; 8th ed. 1920.

12. The offer curve is a demand curve “in the sense that it expresses the demand for one commodity in terms of the supply of another. Ordinary demand curve expresses the demand for varying amounts of a single commodity in terms of money.” The money measured used, is however, price per unit, not total money spent. If the second commodity be regarded as money, which is possible, the offer curve would be a demand curve in terms of

quantity of commodities against total amount of money. It would be a total revenue curve, as opposed to demand curve, average revenue per unit.

13. This law is that “producers, each governed under the sway of free competition by calculation of his own interest, will endeavour so to regulate the amount of any commodity which is produced for a given market during a given period, that this amount shall be just capable on the average of finding purchasers during this period at a remunerative price. A remunerative price is to be interpreted to be a price, which shall be just equal to the sum of the exchange or economic measures of those efforts and sacrifices, which are required for the production of the commodity when the amount in question is produced. These economic measures are the expenses which must be incurred by a person who would purchase the performance of these efforts and sacrifices.”

14. Marshall explained the consumers’ rent as the measures of the surplus or excess of the total value in use to him of the seven tons of coal which he purchases over the value in use of the commodities which he could have obtained by expenditure in other ways the £7 which are the value in exchange of those seven tons..... This value in exchange is of course equal to the measure of the value in use to him of the last ton of the coal which he purchases, or in Mr. Jevons’ phrase to the measure of the final utility of a ton of coal to him. The term consumers’ surplus or rent is Marshall’s but the essential idea – not every detail – Dupit’s.

15. Cournot thus followed standard mathematical practice and placed price as the independent variable on the abscissa and quantity demanded as the dependent variable on the ordinate. Later on Jenkin and Walras did the same. This is in fact usually done in the French literature. But Marshall changed this way of presentation and had the new familiar arrangement of showing prices on the Y axis and quantity on the X axis, and this is usually done in the Anglo-American literature.

16. “The word value, when used without adjunct, always means in political economy, value in exchange.... Exchange value requires to be distinguished from price..... By the price of a things.... we shall understand its value in money; by the value or exchange value of a thing, its general power of purchasing, the command which its possession gives over purchasable commodities in general.”

17. Mill applied the law of demand and supply only to the case where the commodity is absolutely limited in supply (zero elasticity) and he regarded such case as exceptional. The other two categories, viz; where “commodities.... are susceptible of indefinite multiplication without increase of cost” (infinite elasticity) and the intermediate case where commodities “can be multiplied to an indefinite extent” at an increasing marginal cost” (elastic supply), were governed by the consideration of cost of production. Mill assumes constant returns in industry and diminishing returns in agriculture.

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